

The urgent need for tax reform in Australia in the COVID-19 world

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Key findings

- COVID-19 puts pressure on an Australian tax system already under strain from long-term structural forces and the tax-favoured status of certain sources of income.
- Returning Australia to a sound structural budget position over the long term cannot be accomplished through passive action that relies on ‘natural’ revenue growth from current tax sources.
- A public policy priority should be placed on coordinated tax reform actions that are focussed on reducing fiscal vulnerabilities and improving societal wellbeing. An important aspect of reform should be curtailing the amount of economic activity that attracts tax-free status.

What we knew

- The Australian tax mix renders any conversation about meaningful tax reform in Australia largely one about income taxation.
- Major Commonwealth revenue sources are being eroded by a powerful cocktail of long-term forces—globalisation, technological advance, changing consumption trends and taxpayer arbitrage.
- Australia’s heavy reliance on personal and corporate income tax falls heavily on workers. It falls less heavily on other high income earners and wealthy individuals in a manner that is unfair, inefficient and complex.
- Over time, revenue raising is becoming increasingly concentrated onto a narrowing band of high-income taxpayers (individual and corporate) paying high tax rates.

What we do

- Evaluate the soundness of the Australia tax system in light of the government’s initial response to COVID-19.
- Emphasise how tax reform is essential for a sound fiscal foundation in the aftermath of COVID-19.
- Highlight how ‘tax free’ designations on a range of income sources have led to the perverse outcome where it is feasible for someone with household assets worth \$10 million, generating a comfortable income, to pay less tax than someone earning income close to the poverty line.

What we suggest

- The COVID-19 shock and associated public response has revealed that the Australian tax system needs reform – at some point – to ensure it will continue to have the capacity to meet future calls on government.
- Comprehensive tax reform has proved elusive for political reasons and small, incremental changes to the tax system have often been counter-productive.

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- There are two reasons to suspect that Covid-19 has provided a genuinely different (and enabling) context for reform:
 - Australia’s approach since the global financial crisis—of passive, gradual fiscal repair—is insufficient to address the generational challenge of inflated public debt levels.
 - The Covid-19 response can be characterised as a transfer, of both wealth and health, from working age individuals to older generations. The uneven distributional consequences suggest a compensating solution involving an increased tax burden on the holders of existing wealth and a decreased tax burden on the working age population.

What this means for policy

- Tax reform should be an Australian public policy priority.
- The central objectives should be on reducing fiscal vulnerabilities and improving societal wellbeing.
- Reform actions should work to reduce the share of income taxes in the Commonwealth tax mix and more neutrally tax different individuals and different income sources over time.
- A key aspect of reform should be eliminating or dramatically curtailing the amount of economic activity that attracts tax-free status.

Caveats

- The scale of challenge involved in ambitious and comprehensive tax reform resembles something of a Herculean task. The challenges should not be underestimated.
- It’s fundamentally unclear whether there will be enough political willpower, at multiple levels of government, to proceed with reform. The potential window for reform may be narrow.
- Australia has become accustomed to the sort of incremental, piecemeal tax change that will not address the scale of fiscal challenge it now faces.

Where to now?

It is possible that tax reform is consigned as a long-term matter to be resolved during some future fiscal crisis. What we have outlined in this paper is the opportunity for a proactive government to reduce the severity of impacts from such a scenario. We have also highlighted that reform actions that are well targeted can deliver improvements to the tax system and to societal wellbeing.

More information

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 - Full working paper
 - Published version
- We would welcome the opportunity to present our research to your team and to discuss potential joint research projects on related or similar topics.
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